

DECODING QUANTUM, DECODING THE UNIVERSE

Part 2. Earth and Solar System are formed and operated by Quantum.

Mr Tran (email: MrTran2299@gmail.com).

Abstract.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have calculated and discovered the origin of Earth and the Solar System.

Decoding Quantum, decoding the Universe.

QUANTUM are perfect physical entities, have the power to operate the Universe, are the source of all movement. Quantum create all matter, planets, life,... and the majestic Universe.

Nice Earth, be ready to receive the “QUANTUM CODE”, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science, upgrade science and technology to the Quantum level.

Quantum is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Holding the Quantum code, nothing is mysterious anymore.

This scientific work has 8 parts, see details of each part in the separate publication. After scientific community review and confirmation, the entire Quantum code will be published fully. Now, details of part 2 will be published first.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Part 1. Quantum decoding, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science.

The scientist Issac Newton discovered a part of Quantum about 340 years ago.

QUANTUM is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Part 2. Earth and Solar System are formed and operated by Quantum.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have calculated and discovered the origin of Earth and the Solar System.

Part 3. TRANZERAR is origin of the Universe, locate it by a device.

Analyzing observed data in the area of 93 billion light years, combine with Quantum structure, we have discovered that the Universe is formed and operated according to Quantum laws, and invent a device to detect the Tranzerar.

Part 4. Quantum cycle of the Universe, answers the age, beginning, end point and limit of the Universe.

Quantum will let us know the Universe operates according to the Quantum cycle, and will know the limit of the Universe. Analyzing the operation of celestial bodies, will calculate the age of each part of the Universe.

Part 5. The Earth is operated by Quantum, analysis to determine the natural disasters impending.

After studying parts 1-2-3-4, now we have understood everything:

Understanding the Earth operated by Quantum, will know the origin of natural disasters such as volcanoes, earthquakes, tsunamis..., so will determine the time and extent it occurs, will prevent, reduce damage a lot.

Part 6. The interesting origin of the Moon, all phenomena on Earth and in the Universe are no longer mysteries.

The Moon, very close, but we did not expect the Moon to have an extremely interesting history. Very interesting, the mystery will be opened when this part 6 is published in details.

Part 7. Laws and constants of quantum physics.

Some laws and constants of physics to confirm and popularize knowledge about quantum physics. See details in the parts that will be published.

Part 8. Scientific inventions based on Quantum code.

Some scientific inventions and new technology, especially important that you are about to receive, will make life better.

2. CONTENT.

Part 2. Earth and Solar System are formed and operated by Quantum.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have calculated and discovered the origin of Earth and the Solar System as follows:

1. The Sun in mature period.

About 16 billion years ago, when the Sun was a newly matured star, orbiting in the Milky Way galaxy, not as bright as it is now.

(New figures and information, see calculation and verification following or in other part published for more details).

2. The Sun in the period of energy release.

Inside the Sun is operating quantum, compress to accumulate energy over a period of time, to a limit, activate energy release at two levels at different times as follows:

(See part 1 for more details).

2.1. Time of low energy release.

In the near outer layer inside the Sun, Quantum compress energy, to a limit, activate energy release, erupt onto the surface: molten matter, hydrogen,... and energy. Over many times for a long time, hydrogen layer accumulates on the surface thicker and thicker, heated by energy to bright as we see today.

2.2. Time of strong energy release.

In the middle layer inside the Sun, the compression of Quantum potential for a long time, to a limit, activate energy release, big explosion to push matter blocks into space (This is the nova explosion that we often observe in the universe).

3. Matter blocks in the period of collision and merger.

They were pushed into space and divided into three layers:

Layer 1: The matter blocks have thrust plus centrifugal force are smaller than gravity force, so will fall back to the Sun, usually in areas far from the equator where the centrifugal force is small.

Layer 2: near the equator, the matter blocks have thrust plus centrifugal force are greater than gravity force, reaching to greater than the cosmic velocity level 1 and less than level 2, so they move into orbit around the Sun.

$$v_1 = \sqrt{G \cdot M / R} = 72.39 \text{ (km/s)}.$$

They exist many and long time in orbit. After many cycles, they are merged by gravity, when the entire belt merges, a planet will be formed.

In some cases, matter blocks have small mass and far apart, gravity force is not enough to merge, so they are still the asteroid belt orbiting the mother body but cannot to form a planet.

Layer 3: near the equator, the matter blocks have thrust plus centrifugal force very strong, reaching cosmic velocity level 2 or higher, so they quickly move away from the mother body.

$$V_2 = \sqrt{2 \cdot G \cdot M / R} = 102,37(\text{km/s}).$$

They have very high momentum, move quickly toward celestial bodies on near orbit, and have impact on those bodies as follows:

- a. Collide and transfer momentum to the celestial body to move faster, towards merging with the next body.
- b. Causing extinction some the life on the planet of life.

4. The Sun operates the next cycle.

After each the nova explosion, inside the Sun continues compress to accumulate quantum potential a new cycle. Each cycle is about 20-35 million years (see data analysis below).

5. Planets are formed with similar properties.

5.1. Orbit of movement.

They have orbits on the same plane as the equator, same direction of rotation around the axis of the Sun, that is created by thrust and centrifugal force. (If the mother body rotates too slowly, it cannot form a planet system or asteroid belt).

5.2. Velocity of movement around the Sun.

First velocity (celestial bodies just enter orbit) $>V_1 = \sqrt{G \cdot M / R} = 72.39(\text{km/s}).$

Velocity decreases over time with a constant $S_m = 17.95(\%/by).$

(The constant S_m , defined in part 1, that: "Every object moving in space, dominated by Quantum and slowed down by $S_m = 17.95\%$ every billion years").

5.3. Rotational velocity around the axis.

Celestial bodies rotate around their axes with any and different velocities, because the merger momentum is any and different.

5.4. Tilt angle of the rotation axis.

Celestial bodies have the tilt angle of the rotation axis are any and different, because the merger angle is any and different.

5.5. Spiral step away from the Sun.

Celestial bodies move away from the Sun after each orbital cycle, depends on the first velocity and each additional momentum. (See the detail table below).

5.6. Two celestial bodies merge or lock motion.

Celestial bodies moving on the same plane, when they come near each other, will be merged by gravity. If their momentum is large enough to overcome gravity, they will lock motion and become satellites.

5.7. Substructure operated by quantum, similar the Solar System.

Jupiter and big planets have belts, operated by quantum, similar the Solar System above. Scientists can measure and physically analyze the structure of the Jupiter System to verify.

Go through many Quantum operating cycles as above, after 16 billion years, to date the Solar System has formed 8 large planets, many small planets and asteroid belts. All the physics calculations match the scientific data (see data table).

Name	Mass (10^{24} kg)	Rotation period (day)	Axis angle (degree)	Orbital period (year)	Orbital radius (AU)	Velocity (km/s)	Age (B.Year)	Spiral step (m/year)
1. Mercury	0.33	58.65	0.00	0.24	0.40	47.87	2.14	16.10
2. Venus	4.87	243.69	177.30	0.62	0.70	35.02	3.72	21.36
3. Earth	5.97	1.00	23.40	1.00	1.00	29.78	4.54	27.42
4. Mars	0.64	1.03	25.20	1.88	1.50	24.08	5.61	35.53
5. Jupiter	1,899.00	0.41	3.10	11.87	5.20	13.05	8.71	86.62
6. Saturn	568.46	0.44	26.70	29.45	9.50	9.64	10.24	136.66
7. Uranus	86.83	0.72	97.80	84.02	19.60	6.80	12.01	242.70
8. Neptune	102.43	0.67	28.30	164.89	30.00	5.43	13.14	340.52

6. The Earth is formed and operated by Quantum.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have discovered that: The Earth has operated very disastrously for life in the past, and know the future according to the rules.

The Earth has gone through 4.54 billion years, formed and operated as follows:

* **At 1 billion years old**, Earth was just celestial bodies pushed into space by the Sun, forming a belt and in the process of merging.

* **At 2 billion years old**, Earth had merged the entire of belt and formed a small planet, with an orbit similar to that of Mercury today.

* **At 3 billion years old**, Earth had merged add some small planets and reached a mass of 2.8×10^{24} kg, with an orbit similar of Venus today.

* **At 4.29 billion years old**, a very rich ecosystem of life was formed on Earth in the Permian period, 251 million years ago.

At that time, the 2.8×10^{24} kg Earth merged with a planet size 3.16×10^{24} kg (name is Earth B), leading to the life was extinct near-total.

The event happened 251 million years ago, near today, so still exist many traces on the Earth's surface as follows:

a. Looking at the entire surface of Earth, can see two different parts divided by the Pacific Ring of Fire, that is the trace of the merger of two Earths.

b. Part of Earth B is heavier, so gravity pulls water to flow come, forming the Pacific Ocean today.

c. Part of Earth is lighter, became a continent. After cores merged, gravity rounds out the new Earth, causing continent to crack and move to the center of Pacific Ocean, lava rises from the bottom of the crack, water flows in to form the oceans. (clearly visible on the Earth's topography map and verify).

d. Have discovered many traces of the events of 251 million years ago, but looks very mysterious. Now can be clearly decoded.

7. Decoding the extinction of life on Earth.

The Sun has caused the extinction of life on Earth many times.

Based on the quantum operation of the Sun, analyzing archaeological data of Earth's temperature, we have discovered that: about 20-35 million years is a cycle of temperature decrease and then increase sharply, that is due to nova explosion, shoot energy and meteors into Earth, causing extinction events.

The extinction event 251 million years ago was the most catastrophic, caused by the merger of two Earths (see item 6 above).

The extinction event 66 million years ago, caused by the Sun exploded (as item 7), was an event with a large number of big creatures, because before that was a long period of stable life on Earth.

The extinction event 56 million years ago, was unusual and mysterious. Because it is so special, near today, so will be published in a separate part after publish the Quantum decoding.

8. Conclusion.

Much of the physics data and new discoveries above, scientific community can verify the facts.

See details of next part in the separate publication.

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Send email, I will decode all the mysteries of science.

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